

Effect of Electron-withdrawing Groups on Grignard Reaction with Unsaturated Carbonyl Compounds

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It is well known that the mode of addition of Grignard reagents to α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds is influenced by Cu^{I} ions¹. Whereas normal 1,2-addition takes place in the absence of Cu^{I} ions, conjugate addition takes place in their presence. We report herein the unusual and exclusive 1,4-addition of the Grignard reagents to the coumarins, ethyl[5,6]benzocoumarin-3-carboxylate (**1**) and 3-acetyl[5,6]benzocoumarin (**2**) in the absence of Cu^{I} ions. These compounds when reacted with methylmagnesium iodide according to the reported procedure², gave ethyl 4-methyl-3,4-dihydro-[5,6]-benzocoumarin-3-carboxylate (**3**) and 3-acetyl-4-methyl-3,4-dihydro [5,6]benzocoumarin (**4**) respectively. The fact that coumarins **5**³ and **6**⁴ give normal addition products under the same conditions, suggests that the electron-withdrawing acetyl and ethoxy carbonyl groups at 3-position are responsible for this unusual behaviour. The structures of the adducts have been characterised by their spectra.

to a large excess (25 mmol) of methylmagnesium iodide in anhydrous ether under nitrogen atmosphere. The usual work-up gave the adducts **3** and **4** : **3** m.p. 96°, ν_{max} 1715, 1755 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 8.0–7.2 (6H, ArH), 4.27 (1H, d), 4.0 (2H, q), 1.53 (3H, d), 0.97 (3H, t); m/z 284 (M^+ , 17), 211 (100), 168 (32), 115 (33); **4** m.p. 114°, ν_{max} 1715, 1762 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 13.2 (1H, s), 8.0–7.2 (6H, ArH), 4.4 (1H, q), 1.5 (3H, d); m/z 254 (M^+ , 28), 221 (31) 211 (100), 197 (50).

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Experimental

A solution of 2.5 mmol of the coumarins **1** and **2** in dry THF was added with stirring

